

Synthesis of 1,3-Dimethyl-4-amino-5-nitroso-2,6-pyrimidindione and its Derivatives

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1,3-Dimethyl-4-amino-5-nitroso-2,6-pyrimidinedione, hereby referred to as 'nitroso intermediate', is an important intermediate for the manufacture of most common bronchodilators¹. With this in view, 'nitroso intermediate' and its derivatives have been synthesised (Schemes 1 and 2) to explore their bronchodilatory activities.

Results and Discussion

There are several known organic compounds having pyrimidine and/or uracil nuclei with proven clinical activity², such as antibacterial, antiprotozoal, antineoplastic,

diuretic and bronchodilator. Several metal complexes are reported to have antibacterial properties³. Metal complexes have also been helpful in the treatment of cancer⁴. The nitroso intermediate (4) exhibits tautomerism (Scheme 1). The nitroso intermediate (4) and its above synthesised derivatives have pyrimidine and uracil nucleus. Hence these derivatives are expected to show bronchodilatory activity. The bronchodilatory and antineoplastic activities of the above synthesised compounds are under study and the results are awaited.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Experimental

1,3-Dimethyl-4-amino-5-nitroso-2,6-pyrimidindione (4) : 1,3-Dimethylurea (4 g) and acetic anhydride (8 ml) were added to cyanoacetic acid solution and the mixture was heated at 60° . Acetic acid and excess of acetic anhydride were then distilled off at 75° under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in water (100 ml), made alkaline and boiled for 30 min. On cooling, a pale yellow crystalline solid (3; 3.9 g, 50%) was obtained. The dried compound 3 was dissolved in hot water (100 ml) and NaNO_2 (2.2 g) was added to it. A mixture of water (9 ml) and ice (3 g) was then added in small portions with stirring at 50° . The solution was left in a refrigerator overnight. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol to yield 4 (86%), m.p. 239° (Found : C, 38.03; H, 4.14; N, 29.11. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 39.13; H, 4.34; N, 30.43%); λ_{max} (CH₃OH) 227 and 318 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 535 (OH), 3 200 (NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 640 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.5 (2-CH₃), 9.05 (=NH) and 12.96 (=N-OH).

1,3-Ditheophylline-propan-2-ol (8) : A mixture of water (140 ml), iron powder (40 g) and conc. HCl (6 ml) was heated at 90° for 15 min maintaining pH at 5.2. The nitroso intermediate (4; 54 g) was then added slowly to it. Reduction into diamino compound (5) was confirmed during addition by performing spot test. pH was adjusted to 8.5 by adding Na_2CO_3 (~3.8 g) and sodium hydrosulphite (0.5 g) was added for bleaching action. The sludge was allowed to

settle and temperature was maintained at 90° . Upper clear liquid layer was filtered. The sludge was washed with water (3×50 ml) and washings were added to the total filtrate to adjust the pH to 3.47. The temperature was maintained at 90° . To the above solution, 45% caustic lye (85 g) was added with stirring followed by NaCl (60 g). The solution was then cooled to 30° and filtered under vacuum to get sodium theophyllinate (6). Compound 6 (32.5 g) was then dissolved in water (117 ml) and heated to 90° . Its pH was adjusted to 8.3. Then sodium hydrosulphite (0.025 g) and activated charcoal (1 g) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min and filtered. pH of the filtrate was adjusted to 5.0 by adding conc. HCl (2.6 ml) and stirred for 30 min. It was then cooled to 10° to crystallise theophylline (7) which was dried at 150° (69%), m.p. 274° . Compound 7 (5 g) was dissolved in 20% NaOH (40 ml) and refluxed for 2 h. Epichlorohydrine (8 ml) was then added dropwise and refluxed for 4 h. pH was adjusted to 8. The solution was cooled to 2° and kept for 24 h. The white needle shaped crystals obtained were crystallised from methanol, (47%), m.p. 166° (Found : C, 47.9; H, 4.65; N, 28.12. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{O}_5$ calcd. for : C, 49.03; H, 4.80; N, 29.92%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 3 025 (NH), 1 760 (C=O) and 3 025 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Additional derivatives of 'nitroso intermediate' (4) :

1,3-Dimethyl-4-amino-5-benzoylnitroso-2,6-pyrimidindione (9) : Compound 4 (5 g) was dissolved in

dimethylformamide (40 ml) at 70°. Then benzoyl chloride (4.8 ml) was added dropwise and the solution was refluxed for 4 h. The resulting yellowish brown needle shaped crystals were crystallised from ethanol, (78%), m.p. 184° (Found : C, 53.19; H, 3.98; N, 18.88. $C_{13}H_{12}N_4O_4$ calcd. for : C, 54.17; H, 4.16; N, 19.44%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 145 (NH), 1 640 (C=N) and 1 540 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.66 (2- CH_3), 7.34 (ArH) and 8.66 (NH).

1,3-Dimethyl-4-amino-5-nitroso-2,6-pyrimidindione hydrochloride (10) : Compound 4 (10 g) was added to aqua regia (8 ml) cooled to 0° with stirring. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at 5° and then diluted with cold water (200 ml). The resulting white solid was crystallised from methanol, (82%), m.p. 258° (Found : C, 31.82; H, 3.23; N, 24.42. $C_6H_9N_4O_3Cl$ calcd. for : C, 32.63; H, 3.63; N, 25.39%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 545 (OH), 2 980 (NH), 1 780 (C=O) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Condensate product (11) of compound 4 with trichloroacetic acid : To compound 4 (2 g) dissolved in methanol (200 ml), 25% trichloroacetic acid (7 ml) in methanol was added and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h. Methanol was then distilled off to reduce volume to 25 ml. The resulting white crystalline solid was crystallised from benzene, (70%), m.p. 136° (Found : C, 29.64; H, 2.47; N, 17.23. $C_8H_8N_4O_5Cl_2$ calcd. for : C, 30.77; H, 2.88; N, 17.94%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 225 (OH), 3 125 (NH), 1 655 (C=O), 1 545 (C=N) and 760 cm^{-1} (C-Cl).

Cobalt complex (12) : To compound 4 (2.9 g) dissolved in dimethylformamide (100 ml), cobalt chloride solution (70 ml, 4%, w/v) was slowly added and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 45 min. The resulting orange coloured solid was crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. >300° (Found : C, 32.28; H, 3.14; N, 25.78. $C_{12}H_{14}N_8O_6Co$

calcd. for : C, 33.88; H, 3.29; N, 26.35%); λ_{\max} (CH_3OH) 240, 270 and 360 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 130 (NH), 1 670 (C=O) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.06 (2- CH_3) and 3.43 (=NH).

Copper complex (13) : To compound 4 (2 g) dissolved in methanol (150 ml), 1N HCl (25 ml) was added slowly followed by copper acetate solution (10.85 ml; 4%, w/v). Reaction mixture was then heated on a water-bath for 30 min and then methanol was distilled off to reduce the volume to 10 ml. The resulting yellowish needle-shaped crystalline solid was crystallised from methanol, (46%), m.p. >300° (Found : C, 32.81; H, 3.13; N, 25.24. $C_{12}H_{14}N_8O_6Cu$ calcd. for : C, 33.50; H, 3.26; N, 26.07%); ν_{\max} (CH_3OH) 225 and 253 nm; ν_{\max} 3 280 (NH), 1 680 (C=O) and 1 640 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Nickel complex (14) : To compound 4 (2 g) dissolved in dimethylformamide (100 ml), nickel chloride solution (20%; 18 ml) was added under constant stirring. The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 40 min, then cooled in ice and the dark brown crystals obtained were recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, (52%), m.p. >300° (Found : C, 32.71; H, 3.11; N, 25.51. $C_{12}H_{14}N_8O_6Ni$ calcd. for : C, 33.89; H, 3.29; N, 26.36%); ν_{\max} 3 320 (NH), 1 670 (C=O) and 1 570 cm^{-1} (C=N).

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